

CTF/Serpent Coupling for High-Fidelity Transient Analysis of VVER-1000

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ABSTRACT

Ongoing efforts to further develop the state-of-the-art thermal-hydraulics sub-channel code CTF seek to improve applicability to VVER modelling, including updates in the CTF Coupling Interface (CI). The high-fidelity continuous energy Monte Carlo (MC) neutronics code Serpent was recently coupled with CTF to be applicable for triangular lattice/hexagonal geometry Light Water Reactor (LWR) designs. The CI includes both temporal and spatial coupling. A Picard Iteration (PI) method is utilized for coupled steady-state convergence, while an Operator Splitting (OS) approach is used for coupled transient applications. This work aims to present the CTF/Serpent coupling methodology for transient analysis. To test this transient methodology, an assembly model has been generated, based on the VVER-1000 geometry from the ongoing OECD/NEA Rostov-2 benchmark. A Control Rod (CR) insertion fast transient scenario is proposed to test the methodology and propose improvements. While the possibility to use the developed CTF/Serpent coupled code for transient calculations is demonstrated, the excessively long runtimes for large models or long transients may need a different approach. The authors propose a new methodology based on a hybrid high-fidelity CTF/Serpent/PARCS transient scheme. This methodology is currently in development.

Keywords: CTF, Serpent, PARCS, multi-physics, high-fidelity fast transient analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

A crucial part of safety assessments is achieving accurate predictions from computational simulations, particularly where local parameters are of importance. Continuous energy Monte Carlo neutron transport methods can be beneficial to achieve high-fidelity solutions of exact geometries including local parameters. Although Monte Carlo codes often require long simulation times to achieve acceptable levels of statistical uncertainty, recent advances in High Performance Computing (HPC) have enabled the more frequent utilization of Monte Carlo neutron transport codes with continuous energy cross sections for high-fidelity reactor modelling and simulation. These developments also allow the evaluation of local multi-physics behavior using coupled high-fidelity codes.

Under this framework, a loose external coupling between CTF and Serpent was developed for criticality and transient simulations in Cartesian geometry [1]. Subroutines were added to CTF to create interface files for the pin/sub-channel level spatial mapping to Serpent. However, this original coupled code was developed for the analysis of square-lattice Light Water Reactors (LWRs) designs, without sufficient flexibility to be applicable to hexagonal geometries.

Since then, CTF has undergone continuous development and improvement for hexagonal lattice LWRs vessel calculations including the capability to solve fluid conditions considering triangular sub-channel or hexagonal channel descriptions. These capabilities need to be verified in a multi-physics environment where detailed power distribution from a high-fidelity code such as Serpent are used.

This work presents the implementation of a coupling between a high-fidelity Monte Carlo neutronics code Serpent and a thermal-hydraulics sub-channel code CTF to simulate pin-wise/sub-channel scale behavior for hexagonal geometry reactors. The data exchange and convergence checks are facilitated

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by expanding the CTF neutronics coupling interface for steady-state and transient capabilities. Following the development stage, the first step is to demonstrate a preliminary test case to assess the coupling abilities qualitatively. The details of the coupling sequence and the initial transient test results based on control rod movement in a VVER-1000 assembly model are provided in the next sections.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Code Descriptions

CTF [2], a version of COBRA-TF (Coolant Boiling in Rod Arrays-Two Fluid), is developed and maintained by the Reactor Dynamics and Fuel Modelling Group (RDFMG) at North Carolina State University (NCSSU) in cooperation with Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL). CTF is a 3D thermal-hydraulics sub-channel code and uses a two-fluid, three-field modelling approach for light water reactors vessel analysis. A development version of CTF is used in this work. The coupling with Serpent is implemented and currently being improved in the multi-physics interface subroutine of CTF.

Serpent [3], developed and maintained by VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, is a continuous-energy, generalized-geometry Monte Carlo particle transport code. Serpent was selected to be coupled with CTF because it has a universal multi-physics interface facilitating the coupling with external solvers such as CTF. The interface relies on a super-imposed data structure that enables passing temperature and density distributions into the transport simulations without modifications to the underlying geometry. This work employs Serpent version 2.2.1.

2.2. CTF/Serpent Coupling

A Coupling Interface (CI) was developed between CTF and Serpent by taking advantage of the Serpent universal multi-physics interface and the generalized neutron kinetics CTF coupling interface [1]. The data exchange between CTF and Serpent uses interface files as described by Serpent documentation to construct an external, loose coupling. CTF's coupling interface was extended with functions to generate and process these interface files, applying geometric mapping to provide mesh equivalence.

The CTF/Serpent CI includes both temporal and spatial coupling. For steady state, a Picard Iteration (PI) method is used to achieve coupled convergence, while an Operator Splitting (OS) approach is used for transient applications. Other coupling approaches are available in the CTF portion of the coupled calculation, including solution interruption, residual balance, and adaptive residual balance [4]. Spatial mapping is defined through user-inputs to the CI. This methodology provides all necessary intermediate processing of data, performs iteration checks and uses interface file generation as a method of data exchange for steady-state and transient calculations.

Serpent and CTF inputs for the model geometry are generated beforehand. The CTF input is generated by a preprocessor [5] with uniform power distributions in the fuel rods as an initial guess. Serpent utilizes fuel and coolant temperatures as well as coolant density to select the initial cross sections. After reading coolant and fuel information from "cool.ifc" and "fuel.ifc" interface files generated by CTF, Serpent starts in a separate process to calculate the power distribution accounting for thermal-hydraulic feedback while CTF stays on standby waiting for Serpent power shapes.

Serpent has the capability to apply on-the-fly temperature treatment, by explicitly considering the motion of target nuclei at collision sites [3] for the adjustment of cross sections to different temperatures. Doppler temperature is calculated in CTF, to be written to interface files and read by Serpent, using the Santamarina correlation [6] for each fuel pin at each axial node:

$$T_{Doppler} = T_{ave} - \frac{1}{18}(T_{fc} - T_{fs}). \quad (1)$$

where T_{ave} is the average temperature of a fuel pin at a given axial level, T_{fc} is the fuel centerline temperature and T_{fs} is the fuel surface temperature. The cross sections for thermal scattering are determined by interpolating data at various coolant temperatures, removing the need to pre-generate cross section libraries at detailed resolutions.

To ensure convergence despite statistical uncertainties in the power profile, the Serpent built-in under-relaxation method is enabled [3].

A mapping automation script was developed during this work. The mapping script processes the CTF hexagonal pre-processor and creates a CTF input simultaneously to generate “mapping tables” for spatial mesh overlays. The spatial coupling is based on a one-to-one mapping scheme in the axial direction. Given the relatively straightforward spatial mapping, a nested, regular cartesian or hexagonal meshes to be incorporated. This is particularly important for the target application of full-core calculations performed at pin/sub-channel level in the near future.

The coupled steady-state methodology is started by CTF computing the thermal-hydraulic feedback based on the input user defined power profiles. The first thermal-hydraulic solution is then written in the interface files as an initial temperature and density distributions for Serpent. The general description of the CTF/Serpent coupled calculation flow is outlined in Figure 1; the steady-state simulation is ended once both code solutions are converged.

Figure 1. CTF/Serpent coupling scheme for steady-state and transient simulations.

The first power distribution extracted from the Serpent interface output file is used to update the power profiles in CTF fuel rods. The generated neutronic and thermal-hydraulic feedback parameters are processed and exchanged by reading/writing the interface files for each iteration. CTF checks the convergence criteria for the steady-state criticality calculation. When the convergence is reached, CTF terminates and sends a signal for Serpent to do the same. The communication between CTF and Serpent is conducted with an extra communication file that carries specific signals updated at each iteration by both codes. Communication on the Serpent side can be enabled by an input flag indicating the path of the communication files [3].

The coupled local convergence criteria are based on the L_2 and L_∞ norms of the feedback variables residuals. The coupled scheme compares temperatures of fuel and coolant, coolant density, and power profile to those of the previous iteration for user specified convergence criteria. While L_2 checks the

average solution convergence, L_∞ measures the maximum difference across all computation nodes (meshes). Hence, checking both norms in such non-linear problems is the best practice to ensure solution convergence once distributions find both norms within the prescribed tolerance. The convergence of global parameters such as the k-effective are considered by checking the difference (residual) between two successive iterations.

The transient coupled methodology starts with a criticality steady-state simulation run to initialize the time-dependent coupling scheme. The results of the criticality solution are used as a starting point for thermal hydraulic conditions in CTF and an initial neutron source in Serpent together with initial concentrations of delayed neutron precursors for the transient, as shown in Figure 1. The time-dependent simulation applies an Operator Splitting approach, in which each code runs the same time-step before exchanging information and moving on to the next step. This relatively simple approach was selected due to the large computation time associated with the Monte Carlo code where more elaborate methods may result in prohibitive run times. Note that this transient scheme is suitable only for fast-duration transient simulations from a milliseconds to few seconds.

2.3. Verification Test Case

A VVER-1000 assembly model from the Rostov-2 benchmark of OECD/NEA [7] was utilized to test the CTF/Serpent coupled code for transient simulations. The modelled fuel assembly consists of 312 fuel rods with 2.2 w/o enriched UO_2 , 18 guide tubes with control rods at 90% withdrawn positions, and one central instrument tube as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Model of VVER Test Assembly without (left) and with Control Rods (CRs) on XY-Plane (right).

The core conditions were utilized to calculate core-averaged flow in the test model. The axial reflectors, as shown in Figure 3, were included in the neutronics model; black boundary conditions were described at the bottom and the top of the assembly following axial reflectors, while reflective boundary conditions were used in the radial boundaries. The assembly is divided into 20 axial nodes with equal height along the active fuel length in both CTF and Serpent models for one-to-one mapping in the axial direction. Note that axial reflectors were not included in the CTF model since they weren't considered during the coupled calculation.

Figure 3. CRs on XZ-Plane, at 90% withdrawn positions.

Fuel pellets in CTF were split into 10 radial rings where each ring has equal cross-sectional area while each fuel pin is considered one tally cell in Serpent. A sub-channel centered CTF geometry was overlaid over the fuel-pin centered Serpent model. The thermal-hydraulic data is exchanged for fuel cells and surrounding coolant, while guide tubes and reflectors are maintained at core average temperatures in the Serpent calculation. The steady state initial core conditions before control rod movement are given in Table I. The details regarding the dimensions and material information can be found in Rostov-2 benchmark specifications [7].

Table I. Assembly steady-state conditions.

Parameter	Value
Assembly total power (MW)	9.2
Pressure (MPa)	15.7
Inlet Temperature (°C)	290
Coolant mass flowrate (kg/s)	110.0
CR position (% withdrawn)	90.0

The proposed transient scenario involves CR insertion as depicted in Figure 4. During the criticality calculation and the first 0.5 seconds of the time-dependent simulation of the coupling, the CR is positioned 90% withdrawn from the bottom of the active fuel length. The CR moves downward with fixed velocity for the next 1 second. The system is allowed to evolve until the time reaches 8 seconds.

Figure 4. CR position over time during transient.

The coupled steady-state calculation was performed using 10^6 particles per cycle with 150 inactive and 100 active cycles in each iteration to save initial source distribution to be used in dynamic MC mode of Serpent which informs starting concentrations of delayed neutron precursors and live neutrons going into the coupled transient simulation. Finally, the transient scenario was performed using 800-time bins, with a user-defined 10 ms timestep size.

2.4. Results

In both steady-state and transient steps of the coupled simulation, the ENDF/B-VII cross-section library is utilized. The steady-state simulation is converged in 48 global coupled iteration with k-effective 1.21441. The converged steady-state temperature distribution shown in Figure 5 was used in transient simulation as initial conditions. The maximum change between the inlet and outlet coolant temperature was 20 °C. The fuel temperature was heavily bottomed since the CR was inserted 10% of the active height from the top of the fuel.

The transient power level obtained from the simulation is illustrated in the left side of Figure 6, compared to a Serpent standalone simulation for the same case. Power rapidly decreases following the control rod insertion at 0.5 seconds. The right side of Figure 6 illustrates the decreasing assembly outlet coolant temperature with time.

The transient was run on 2880 CPUs in total for Serpent calculation with hybrid MPI/OMP parallelization on Idaho National Laboratory Sawtooth 1 HPC while CTF was run sequentially on one CPU. For a total length of the transient of 8 seconds, the simulation required approximately 7 days to complete. This highlights the computational burden of dynamic Monte Carlo simulations. There is a need for acceleration strategies including alternative approaches, such as developing hybrid quasi-static dynamic methodological framework that provides faster performance while maintaining acceptable accuracy [8-9].

Figure 5. Assembly coolant temperature (top-left), radial pin power (top-right) and fuel temperature (bottom).

Figure 6. Transient power level and coolant temperature calculated by coupled code.

2.5. Alternative Hybrid Transient Coupled Methodology

Applying the full dynamic Monte Carlo scheme with sub-channel thermal-hydraulic feedback to more comprehensive and complex scenarios, such a full-core model with longer transient cases could be computationally prohibitive. To make such high-fidelity analyses practical for full-core transients, a hybrid quasi-static dynamic methodological framework and corresponding coupling strategy are adopted where the flux shape is updated periodically using Monte Carlo calculations while the time-dependent flux amplitude is evaluated more frequently through deterministic methods. This approach is expected to significantly reduce computational costs without sacrificing essential physics. This hybrid coupling is expected to be of primary benefit to slow or long duration transients, where it is impractical to perform CTF/Serpent calculations and where quasi-static approaches are most applicable.

Under this framework, CTF/Serpent can be used periodically to compute accurate flux shape functions at coarse time intervals and/or static mode, while a nodal diffusion/thermal-hydraulic code coupling, such as PARCS [10] coupled to CTF, performs lower fidelity transient calculations at a finer time resolution to capture time-dependent neutron flux amplitude evolution. The transient would be initialized from a steady state solution, which is found by CTF/PARCS with Serpent-informed pin powers used in CTF. Serpent uses thermal hydraulic data from CTF while using PARCS results as a fixed source at the iteration or time where pin powers are to be updated. This hybrid workflow, shown in Figure 7, may balance accuracy and computational efficiency, enabling realistic transient modeling with thermal-hydraulic feedback while remaining compatible with existing simulation tools. In this way, major approximations in space and time will be avoided by integrating Serpent into transient CTF/PARCS calculations for detailed analysis, since it uses continuous energy cross sections. Moreover, it does not require additional measures such as pin power reconstruction to obtain 3-D pin powers. The

development of this alternative hybrid transient coupling methodology is underway, and results will be shared as they become available.

Results of an initial test demonstrating the capability to synchronize powers between Serpent and PARCS for the hybrid coupling via the use of PARCS output data as a fixed source in Serpent are shown in Figure 8. This capability to inform CTF/Serpent prevents the need to run Serpent in transient mode or account separately for source calculations which can become burdensome, instead relying upon the much faster CTF/PARCS calculations. This has the added benefit of improving the consistency of Serpent and PARCS powers used together to inform the CTF pin power distributions.

Figure 7. Quasi-deterministic hybrid CTF/Serpent/PARCS approach.

Figure 8. Axial power distribution of Serpent using PARCS source for hybrid synchronization.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The work presented in this paper showed the initial transient capabilities of the coupling developed between the high-fidelity neutronic code Serpent and the thermal-hydraulic sub-channel code CTF for hexagonal geometry reactors. The coupled simulation uses a fine resolution at the pin-wise/sub-channel

level to obtain high fidelity results. Picard iteration was used for the steady-state criticality calculation, while Operator Splitting (OS) is considered for coupled transient modeling applications.

The codes were coupled semi-internally by enhancing the CTF neutronic coupling interface. The coupling consists of subroutines that process spatial mapping tables and other necessary steps to facilitate the exchange of thermal-hydraulics and neutronics fields. The initial capabilities of the coupled code have been demonstrated by modeling a VVER-1000 fuel assembly with control rod insertion. The next steps include further investigation into the different scenarios, later continuing with the validation and verification process.

Considering the burden on computational resources, as tested and presented here, future work is planned to apply a novel strategy to achieve results on a full core transient event case. For this, a hybrid coupling between CTF/Serpent and CTF/PARCS was proposed to be embedded inside of a quasi-static dynamics framework, and the implementation is currently in development. With this approach, accuracy and computational efficiency can be balanced, enabling realistic transient high-fidelity MC neutronics modeling with thermal-hydraulic feedback using existing simulation tools.

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